

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**
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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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ETIOLOGICAL FACTORS AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILDREN WITH ACUTE BRONCHIOLITIS**Azimova K.T.**

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Resume. The article presents the results of a study on the etiological structure and clinical characteristics of acute bronchiolitis in infants. A total of 94 cases of acute bronchiolitis in children aged from 1 to 7 months were analyzed. Respiratory syncytial virus was identified as the main etiological factor in 71.3% of patients. The seasonality of the disease, clinical manifestations, respiratory failure characteristics, and physical findings in the lungs were investigated. The obtained data confirm the leading role of RSV infection in the development of bronchiolitis in infants.

Keywords: acute bronchiolitis, infants, respiratory syncytial virus, PCR diagnostics, respiratory failure, viral infections.

ЎТКИР БРОНХИОЛИТ БИЛАН КАСАЛЛАНГАН БОЛАЛАРДА ЭТИОЛОГИК ОМИЛЛАР ВА КЛИНИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАР**Азимова К.Т.**

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Резюме. Мақолада гўдак ёшидаги болаларда ўткир бронхиолитнинг этиологик тузилиши ва клиник хусусиятларини ўрганиш натижалари келтирилган. 1 ойликдан 7 ойликкача бўлган болаларда кузатилган 94 та ўткир бронхиолит ҳолати таҳлил қилинди. Касалликнинг асосий этиологик омили сифатида беморларнинг 71,3 фоизда аниқланган респиратор-синцитиал вирус (РСВ) қайд этилди. Касалликнинг мавсумийлиги, клиник намоён бўлиши, нафас етишимовчилигининг хусусиятлари ҳамда ўпкадаги физик текширув натижалари ўрганилди. Олинган маълумотлар гўдак ёшидаги болаларда бронхиолит ривожланишида РСВ инфекциясининг етакчи ўрин тутушини тасдиқлайди.

Калим сўзлар: ўткир бронхиолит, гўдак ёшидаги болалар, респиратор-синцитиал вирус, ПЗР (ПЦР) диагностикаси, нафас етишимовчилиги, вирусли инфекциялар.

ЭТИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ДЕТЕЙ С ОСТРЫМ БРОНХИОЛИТОМ**Азимова К.Т.**

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Резюме. В статье представлены результаты исследования этиологической структуры и клинических особенностей острого бронхиолита у детей грудного возраста. Проведен анализ 94 случаев острого бронхиолита у детей в возрасте от 1 до 7 месяцев. Основным этиологическим фактором заболевания был выявлен респираторно-синцитиальный вирус (РСВ), обнаруженный у 71,3% пациентов. Изучены сезонность заболевания, клинические проявления, особенности дыхательной недостаточности и физикальные изменения в легких. Полученные данные подтверждают ведущую роль РСВ-инфекции в развитии бронхиолита у детей грудного возраста.

Ключевые слова: острый бронхиолит, дети грудного возраста, респираторно-синцитиальный вирус, ПЦР-диагностика, дыхательная недостаточность, вирусные инфекции.

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Introduction. Acute bronchiolitis is one of the most common causes of hospitalization among infants and remains an important medical and social problem in modern pediatrics. The disease is characterized by inflammation of the small bronchi and bronchioles with the development of bronchial obstruction syndrome and respiratory failure. Respiratory syncytial virus infection is considered the leading etiological factor in young children.

Despite numerous studies devoted to bronchiolitis, issues related to the etiological structure and clinical features of the disease in infants remain relevant. Investigation of these factors is important for early diagnosis, assessment of disease severity, and selection of optimal treatment strategies.

Aim of the Study. To investigate the etiological factors and clinical characteristics of acute bronchiolitis in infants.

Materials and Methods. A total of 94 children with acute bronchiolitis who were hospitalized were examined. The age of the patients ranged from 1 to 7 months, with a mean age of 5.33 ± 0.29 months.

All children underwent:

- clinical examination;
- assessment of medical history;
- physical examination of the respiratory system;
- polymerase chain reaction (PCR) testing of blood serum to identify etiological agents.

Statistical analysis was performed using generally accepted methods of variation statistics.

Results and Discussion. The study of disease seasonality demonstrated that the highest incidence of acute bronchiolitis occurred during the autumn-winter period. The peak incidence was observed in November — 34.0% (32 children) and December — 29.8% (28 children). In January, the disease was registered in 21.3% (20 children). The remaining cases were observed from September to March and accounted for 15.0% (14 children).

These findings indicate a pronounced seasonal pattern corresponding to the epidemiological circulation of respiratory syncytial virus.

PCR investigation revealed that the main etiological factor of acute bronchiolitis was respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), detected in 71.3% (67 children). RSV mono-infection was identified in 45.7% of patients (43 children).

Among mixed infections, RSV was most frequently combined with adenovirus, parainfluenza virus, and rhinovirus infections — 15.0% (14 children). Combinations of RSV with intracellular pathogens were also detected:

- *Mycoplasma pneumoniae* — 6.4% (6 children);
- *Chlamydia pneumoniae* — 4.3% (4 children).

In children aged 2–6 months, isolated cases of bronchiolitis caused solely by *Chlamydia pneumoniae* were observed — 2.12% (2 children).

Rhinovirus mono-infection was detected in 12.8% (12 children), adenovirus mono-infection in 6.4% (6 children), and parainfluenza virus mono-infection in 5.3% (5 children). Thus, the etiological structure of acute bronchiolitis obtained in the present study corresponds to international data indicating the predominant role of RSV infection in infants.

Analysis of disease history showed that the disease onset was gradual in the majority of patients — 67.0% (63 children). Acute onset was observed in 33.0% (31 children).

The most common clinical manifestations included:

- deterioration of general condition, lethargy, irritability, and refusal to breastfeed — 93.6% (88 children);
- catarrhal symptoms (rhinitis, sneezing, conjunctivitis) — 47.9% (45 children);
- episodes of apnea at disease onset — 12.8% (12 children), and during disease progression — 8.5% (8 children).

Body temperature was predominantly subfebrile in 54.2% of children (51 patients). Febrile fever was noted in 27.6% (26 children), while normal body temperature was maintained in 18.1% (17 children).

Assessment of disease severity demonstrated that severe condition was observed in 68.1% of patients (64 children), moderately severe condition in 27.6% (26 children), and extremely severe condition in 4.3% (4 children).

Clinical manifestations of respiratory failure included:

- expiratory dyspnea — 87.2%;
- involvement of accessory respiratory muscles — 88.3%;
- cyanosis of the nasolabial triangle — 56.4%.

Physical examination of the lungs most frequently revealed:

- hyperresonant percussion sound — 95.7%;
- fine moist crackles — 96.8%;
- crepitation — 83.0%;
- dry wheezing rales — 60.6%.

These findings indicate significant bronchiolar involvement and development of bronchial obstruction syndrome in the majority of examined children.

Conclusion. Acute bronchiolitis in infants is characterized by pronounced seasonality with the highest incidence observed from November to January.

Respiratory syncytial virus is the leading etiological factor, detected in 71.3% of patients.

The clinical course of the disease is characterized by gradual onset, signs of respiratory failure, and pronounced bronchial obstruction syndrome.

The most common physical findings were fine moist crackles, crepitation, and hyperresonant percussion sound.

The obtained data confirm the necessity of early diagnosis of viral etiology and timely correction of respiratory disorders in infants with acute bronchiolitis.

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